

Forecasting Electricity Demand Per Capita Using Generalized Linear Models

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents static models based on Generalized Linear Models (GLM) to forecast electricity demand per capita in Nigeria. It considered that socioeconomic variables such as gross domestic product, population, temperature and consumer price index are factors that directly or indirectly influence electricity demand per capita. The research employs data from 1971 to 2010 using different variants of GLMs to predict the electricity demand per capita in Nigeria from 2011 to 2050. The GLM Gaussian family power 2 link function model was found to be the most preferred model to estimate electricity demand per capita among different models investigated in this study with a forecast results that shows the growth of electricity demand per capita at the annual rate of 38.9% from 120.4859 kWh per capita in 2011 to 167.3775 kWh per capita in 2050. The study provides valuable insight for policy makers and professionals involved in electricity generation, transmission and distribution, and power system management in Nigeria to curb incessant grid collapse and electricity crisis in the country.

Keywords: Electricity, power generation; distribution companies; renewable energy; generalized linear model

INTRODUCTION

Economic development and growth of any economy depends on the availability of high quality and reliable electric power supplies and efficiency of its operators. Nigeria is one of the leading economies in sub-Saharan Africa and one of the most attractive investment destinations in Africa due to her large population and abundant natural resources. Nigeria is a

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developing country with huge demands for electricity due to appreciable growth in its economy-driven by the oil and gas, and non-oil industries. The economic activities have been stimulated by economic reforms and increase in public investment and thus Nigeria has witnessed increasing economic growth rates in the last two decades (Obi & Iloh, 2015). Thus, electricity sector in Nigeria is expanding and changing dynamically. Therefore, the need for a robust and effective prediction model in Nigeria to help industry players plan ahead cannot be over emphasized.

In addition, electricity demand forecast plays significant functions for government, energy industry and private sectors in making precise or informed decisions regarding energy management practices (Asumadu-Sarkodie & Owusu, 2016, Olabode et al., 2018). Adequate planning and right decision making in the energy sector lies on accurate forecasts of the load demand. An accurate forecasting can help a country to plan the use of alternative or renewable energy to reduce dependency on fossil fuel to generate electricity. Electricity demand forecasting is not only important for cost efficient investment in power systems but also useful for setting tariffs and capacity planning and expansion (Akay & Atak, 2006). The electricity forecasting studies have become necessary for many countries to develop policies to address their growing energy demands in order to sustain their economic growth.

Outside the popular machine learning models, several efforts have been made to forecast electricity demand using statistical and econometric models in the literature (Nasr et al, 2000; Kankal et al., 2011; Avdaković et al., 2011; Hasanov et al, 2016; Meher, 2020). Pao (2009) applied state space models to model and forecast electricity consumption in Taiwan. Filik et al. (2011) unlike other long-term forecasting models, the authors' proposed method produces hourly results with improved accuracy. The model is constructed and verified using 26-year-long real-life load data (4 years with hourly resolution) obtained from the Turkish Electric Power Company.

Ohtsuka and Kakamu (2013) analysed electricity demands in Japan for a period of 11 years. The study found that vector autoregressive (VAR) model had better forecasting performance than the spatial autoregressive ARMA (SAR-ARMA). Akay et al. (2020) examined the relationship between per capita electricity consumption and gross domestic

product among selected developed, developing and under-developed countries. The results of the study showed that electricity consumption differs according to the level of development of the countries in terms of technology and industrial saturation.

Prior studies have shown that variables influencing demand for electricity consumption vary from one country to another. A model developed for one country may not be suitable to forecast electricity consumption in another country. Thus, it is essential for distinct models may be developed for different regions or nations for effective energy planning (Pao, 2006). Extant literature shows that several studies (Samuel & Phebe, 2016; Maku et al., 2023; Okakwu et al., 2019; Maku et al., 2023, Popoola & Akanji, 2024) have utilized alternative statistical methods to predict the Nigeria's electricity consumption. These studies offer valuable insights into the factors influencing electricity demand and the effectiveness of various forecasting techniques. These studies do not specifically utilize Generalized Linear Models (GLMs), they provide a foundation for understanding the methodologies applied in forecasting electricity demand in Nigeria.

This current study investigates electricity demand per capita forecasting in Nigeria using GDP, consumer price index, average annual temperature, energy consumption/demand and population as selected variables which are considered very critical determinants of electricity consumption in Nigeria using variants of generalized linear models. They are models that enable regression of normal and non-normal data to be modeled especially when the general regression assumptions will not be satisfied. Each of the independent variables and electricity demand were considered taking into account the strength of relationship between each of the independent variables and the electricity demand per capita.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Modelling approaches are briefly explained in Section 2. Results of electricity demand forecasting obtained by the models are presented in Section 3 in addition to future projections. Finally, the concluding remarks are stated in Section 4 with suggestions on future researches.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Electricity Supply and Demand in Nigeria

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The history of Nigerian Electricity industry has been thoroughly explained in Awosope (2014) and thus no attempt will be made here. However, there is serious crisis in the Nigerian Electricity sector. The demand for electricity in Nigeria is far more than the supply (Sambo, 2008). There is acute shortage of electricity supply in Nigeria which is evident as the abnormal scenarios like load shedding, large line losses, and black-out and system collapse. This has hindered the economic growth of the country in spite of her great potentials and abundant natural resources.

Electricity is generated mainly through non-renewable and alternative energy sources. For instance, coal was used in Nigeria beginning from the early part of twentieth century as the first major source of electricity in Nigeria up till the middle of twentieth century.

However, with the discovery of crude oil and natural gas in commercial quantities in Nigeria and coupled with highly efficient thermal power stations, consumption of coal for electricity in Nigeria was phased out. The natural gas is now utilized to generate electricity through the thermal power stations. In Nigeria, there are power stations formerly owned by the Nigerian Government but have been privatized. These include Egbin, Afam, Ijora, Ughelli/Delta, and Sapele thermal stations. Also, private entities were licensed as independent power producers in Nigeria. Among them are Alaoji, Azura, Ihovbor, Geregu, Kudenda, Ikot Abasi, Okapi, Omoku, Ogorode, Omotosho, Olorunsogo power stations. There are other new independent power producers that have been licensed, planned and preparing for operations. These are AES barge, Aba, Calabar and Egbema power stations. The installed capacity and available capacity of the thermal power plants in Nigeria is appropriately 9044 MW and 6079.6 MW respectively (Obi & Iloh, 2015).

Nigeria is endowed with a large River Niger which is serving as source of hydro-power electricity. The hydro-power stations are located at Jebba, Kanji and Shiroro in Niger State while new ones under construction are Zamfara, Mambilla, Kano and Dadin Kowa hydroelectric stations. The installed capacity and available capacity of the hydropower stations in Nigeria is appropriately 1938 MW and 1060 MW respectively. The hydropower constitutes 27% of electricity supply to the national grid while the natural gas accounted for

72%. The Nigerian power sector has not less than twenty three (23) grid-connected generating plants with the available capacity of 7139.6 MW.

The Nigerian Bulk Electricity Trading plc (NBET) purchases power generated by the Generating companies and independent power producers at the agreed prices and resells to the Distribution companies who service the end consumers. The power industry in Nigeria has been undergoing reform for the past two decades to be able to deliver better and efficient services to Nigerians. The National Integrated Power Project (NIPP) was instituted to boost the generation capacity of the nation by allowing the private sector power producers to own power plants and sell bulk electricity to the distributions companies. The implication of the NIPP has added not less than 1,500 MW to the generation capacity of the Country not considering the challenges of gas supply, insecurity and pipeline vandalism (Obi & Iloh, 2015). The generation and distribution components have been privatized while transmission remains under the ownership and control of the Nigerian government.

The Nigerian Electricity Supply Industry has six (6) generating companies, one (1) transmission company and eleven (11) distribution companies. The Nigerian grid is made of twenty six (26) buses, forty (40) transmission lines and fourteen (14) generating stations. The transmission network is operated at two voltage level, 330KV and 132KV. There is a 5,523.8 Km of 330 KV lines and 6,801.5 Km of 132 KV lines. The 300 kV lines served twenty three substations employing transformers with voltage rating of 330/132 KV. Similarly, the 132 KV lines fed 91 substations using transformers of 132/33 KV. The system frequency is 50 Hz (Samuel et al., 2012).

Transmission Company of Nigeria operates two Control Centres. The main National Control Centre is located at Osogbo while the supplementary National Control Centre is at Shiroro. However, the operations of these control centres are yet to be fully automated due to absence of robust and effective energy management system (EMS) and Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA). The Control Centres regrettably use unreliable and manual approach to control, operate and analyze the Nigerian power system. Thus, the national grid is highly stressed, weak and prone to instability and not flexible. This has seriously hindered the social, economic and industrial development of Nigeria.

Nigerian business owners are closing their business and relocating from the countries due to the erratic power supplies. The country is losing millions of dollars daily for its inability to supply stable power supplies to end users through the national grid. The peak power generated in the last five years is far below 5,000MW whereas the installed capacity is 10,396MW. This is inadequate when compared to the demand forecast of 40,000 MW (Obi & Iloh, 2015). Although, there are planned efforts to increase the total electricity generation to be more than 20,000MW, it is envisaged that this will be achieved when the newly licensed independent power producers and Mabilla hydropower project are fully in operation.

In order to have stable and steady power supply in Nigeria, there is a pressing need to build and operate viable generating stations, expand the transmission and establish resilient distribution networks. Also, the issues of electricity theft, vandalization of electricity infrastructure, poor maintenance culture, overloading or faulty equipment or substations must addressed squarely while residential and government entities must pay for services enjoyed without sabotaging the investment of the distribution companies. These are crucial to keep pace with the substantial growth in the Nigerian economy (Amlabu et al., 2013).

Generalized Linear Models

Generalized linear models are unified models for regression analysis of discrete or continuous response variables. They can be applied to many different types of data with varied distributional characteristics. They are powerful and flexible models used in real world problems where error terms and response variables are normally distributed. Link function is one of the properties of generalized linear model that connects the parameters of the response variable distribution with the linear model. If there exists an appropriate link function for fitting generalized linear models, the goodness of fit of the models may give a better result than linear regression models. The relationship between the set of predictor variables and the response variable could be represented by a set of link functions (Özenboy & Tekir, 2019).

The generalized linear model (GLM) is the generalization of ordinary linear regression models to encompass non-normal distributions and nonlinear functions of the mean. It is made of three components (Mamun & Paul, 2023):

The random component: This describes the response variable y and its probability distribution.

The systematic component: This connects a set of covariates with linear predictor in the following form:

$$\eta = \sum_{j=1}^p X_j \beta_j \tag{1}$$

The link function: This function plays an important role in the analysis of generalized linear models. It provides the relationship between the linear predictor and the mean of the distribution function. It is a monotone differentiable function f applied to each component of $E(y)$, which connects the random and systematic component through $\eta=f(E(y))$.

The random variable Y has a distribution of the generalised linear model form if

$$f(y;\theta)=\exp[a(\theta)y-g(\theta)+c(y)] \tag{2}$$

where $\theta=\eta=X\beta$.

In generalized linear models, $V(\mu)$ is a variance function that characterizes a particular GLM family of distributions. A set of covariates x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k is related to the mean μ by $\theta(\mu)=X\beta$, where θ is the link function, $X=[x_{ir}]$ is an $n \times p$ matrix, and $\beta=(\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_p)'$ is the vector of regression parameters. Furthermore, it is assumed that $x_{i0}=1$ so that β_0 is the intercept parameter (Özenboy, & Tekir, 2019):

The generalized linear models of y with covariates x

$$g\{E(y)\} = x\beta, \quad y \sim F \tag{3}$$

where $g(\cdot)$ is called the link function, and F is the distributed family.

If y is distributed as Gaussian (normal) and $g(\cdot)$ is the identity, thus the expression becomes

$$E(y) = \mu = x\beta, \quad y \sim Normal \tag{4}$$

If y is distributed as Gaussian (normal) and $g(\cdot)$ is the log, thus the expression becomes

$$E(y) = \ln(\mu) = x\beta, \quad y \sim Normal \tag{5}$$

If y is distributed as Gaussian (normal) and $g(\cdot)$ is the power, thus the expression becomes

$$E(y)=\mu^n = x\beta \quad y \sim Normal \tag{6}$$

If y is distributed as Gaussian (normal) and $g(\cdot)$ is the reciprocal, thus the expression becomes

$$E(y) = \mu^{-1} = x\beta \quad y \sim Normal \quad (7)$$

Data and model specifications

The annual data used for this study are available in the World Bank website. The data covers a period from 1971 to 2010. The yearly electricity demand per capita, EEC , is expressed in kilowatts-hour per capita and is taken as the proxy for electricity demand. Gross domestic product is measured as the total quantity of goods and services an economy produced over a period of time. It measures the value of final goods and services produced within a country in one year. It is a metric showing the total economic output of a country represented by all goods produced and services rendered by residents and non-residents within a country. It is represented by GDP . Consumer price index represents increases in the cost of purchasing a basket of products and services to the average customer that can be set or adjusted at prescribed intervals, such as annually. This shows the average price shift customers are paying over a time. It is used as proxy for price of electricity in Nigeria and denoted by CPI . The number of persons living in a country is known as the total population. It is assumed that population has direct and positive effect on electricity demand in a country. It is denoted by POP in this study. Temperature is acknowledged as an important determinant. Demand for electricity increases all through the year either during rainy, harmattan or hot seasons in Nigeria. Temperature is denoted by TMP . During the rainy and harmattan seasons, much of electricity is used for heating while during the hot season, electric energy is needed for cooling (Schneider, 2022).

The study proposed a static model to model electricity demand per capita in Nigeria. The model relates per capita electricity consumption to population, consumer price index, average annual temperature, gross domestic product. It is assumed that the electricity demand per capita depends on these explorative variables. The response or explained variable is the electricity demand while the explanatory or independent variables are the population, gross domestic products, consumer price index and temperature.

$$EEC_t = f(POP_t \ CPI_t \ TMP_t \ GDP_t) \quad (8)$$

The generalized linear models investigated in this study are:

$$\text{glm EEC POP CPI TMP GDP, family(gaussian) link(identity)} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{glm EEC POP CPI TMP GDP, family(gaussian) link(log)} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{glm EEC POP CPI TMP GDP, family(gaussian) link(power 2)} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{glm EEC POP CPI TMP GDP, family(gaussian) link(reciprocal)} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{glm EEC POP CPI TMP GDP, family(poisson) link(identity)} \quad (13)$$

$$\text{glm EEC POP CPI TMP GDP, family(poisson) link(log)} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{glm EEC POP CPI TMP GDP, family(poisson) link(power 2)} \quad (15)$$

$$\text{glm EEC POP CPI TMP GDP, family(poisson) link(reciprocal)} \quad (16)$$

$$\text{glm EEC POP CPI TMP GDP, family(gamma) link(identity)} \quad (17)$$

$$\text{glm EEC POP CPI TMP GDP, family(gamma) link(log)} \quad (18)$$

$$\text{glm EEC POP CPI TMP GDP, family(gamma) link(power 2)} \quad (19)$$

$$\text{glm EEC POP CPI TMP GDP, family(gamma) link(reciprocal)} \quad (20)$$

$$\text{glm EEC POP CPI TMP GDP, family(igaussian) link(identity)} \quad (21)$$

$$\text{glm EEC POP CPI TMP GDP, family(igaussian) link(log)} \quad (22)$$

$$\text{glm EEC POP CPI TMP GDP, family(igaussian) link(power 2)} \quad (23)$$

$$\text{glm EEC POP CPI TMP GDP, family(igaussian) link(reciprocal)} \quad (24)$$

Forecasting error analysis

The sixteen models (9) - (24) were compared to determine the best predicting model(s) over the period under consideration. In this study, two statistical measures are used to compare the relative performance of the models.

Akaike information criterion

Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) is useful to evaluate goodness of fit of a model. It is a performance evaluation criterion that determines which model among multiple models is most likely to be the best model for a given data set. A lowest AIC value is an indication of the best model. AIC is useful for time series and selection of models. AIC selects more complex model as the best. AIC can be defined as:

$$AIC = -2\log L + 2K \quad (25)$$

where L represents the maximum likelihood of the model, K is the number of parameters in the model.

Bayesian Information Criterion

It is an index used to compare and select the best models among several or alternative models. The model with the lowest BIC is considered the best. BIC resolves over-fitting problem in models by introducing a penalty term for the number of parameters in the model. It attempts to strike a balance between model fit and complexity, preventing over fitting and reducing the risk of capturing noises or irrelevant features in data. BIC is more disposed to choose models that are too simple because, it heavily penalizes model complexity. BIC can be defined as

$$BIC = \ln(n)k - 2\ln(L) \quad (26)$$

where n represents sample size, L represents the maximum likelihood of the model, and k is the number of parameters in the model.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Analysis

The data used in this study covered a period of 40 years from 1971 to 2010. The descriptive statistics values of the variables *EEC* *POP* *GDP* *TMP* *CPI* are shown in Table 1.

The relativity of each variable to one another is shown in Table 2. The scatterplot matrix is shown graphically in Figure 2. It shows the general relationships between the

variables and identifying the potential collinearity problem among the dependent variables. Figure 1 shows that the relationship between *CPI* and *POP* is very strong. It indicates that the strong linear dependence might be a source of collinearity problems. The study proposed to remove either *POP* or *CPI* variables from the model but the resulting models did not improve. Therefore, it was decided to be included all the variables in the model (Mohamed & Bodger, 2005).

The normal probability plot of the standardized residuals and the plot of standardized residuals against the fitted values are shown in Figures 2 and 3, respectively. The normal probability plot shows the distribution of the residuals is not dispersed from the normality. Figure 3 shows that the residuals produced by the model are satisfactory. The historical data in the plot are scattered and spread fairly along the horizontal plane. Thus, the residuals behaved randomly and no additional explanatory variable(s) is needed in the model.

Forecasting Performance Comparison of the models

The forecasting abilities of generalized linear models were compared with each other. For the performance evaluation, the predictive accuracies of the models for electricity demand per capita in Nigeria are compared over four different forecast horizons. The in-sample forecast horizon was selected as 10 years, 20 years and 30 years. The results of the four forecast horizons are shown in Tables 3 to 6.

The AIC and BIC values were obtained using the Stata 15 for the modeling. The results in each of the tables show that the models with link function of power 2 in each of the four families yielded the lowest AIC and BIC. Thus, the following models were found to perform best among them:

The four models (27) - (30) were compared using the forty years forecast horizon to determine the best model. From Table 7, it is noted that the model with generalized linear model with Gaussian family and link function of power 2 has the least AIC value while model with inverse Gaussian family with power 2 link function has the least BIC value. The implication is that generalized linear model with Gaussian family has the best simple model

while the model with inverse Gaussian family has the best complex model. The two models are used to predict out of sample from 2011 to 2050.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the variables from 1971 to 2014

Variables	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Standard Deviation	Kurtosis	Skewness
EEC	88.38849	28.80135	154.1723	32.4883	2.398483	.1554549
POP	1.07e+08	5.68e+07	1.79e+08	3.61e+07	2.008326	.3971593
CPI	30.31067	.115048	145.7992	41.78954	3.748143	1.368867
TMP	27.25841	26.68	28.1	.3305945	2.809066	.3750931
GDP	1143.637	161.5439	3200.953	806.8694	2.767268	.935109

Table 2: Correlation matrix of independent variables

Variables	EEC	POP	CPI	TMP	GDP
EEC	1.0000				
POP	0.9120	1.0000			
CPI	0.8282	0.9260	1.0000		
TMP	0.6737	0.6996	0.6294	1.0000	
GDP	0.7089	0.7442	0.8180	0.5155	1.0000

Fig. 1 Scatterplot matrix of electricity consumption and explaining variables used

Fig 2 Normal probability plot of standardized residuals

Figure 3 Standardised residuals against predicted values

Table 3: Performance comparison of GLM Gaussian family with four different links

Forecasting Period	Performance Criteria	GLM family (Gaussian) Link (identity)	GLM family (Gaussian) Link(log)	GLM family (Gaussian) Link (power 2)	GLM family (Gaussian) Link (reciprocal)
1971 – 1980 (10 years)	AIC	6.0315	6.397	5.740	6.595
	BIC	78.1670	117.801	55.5085	178.611
1971 – 1990 (20 years)	AIC	7.212	7.44	7.014	7.536
	BIC	918.25	1170.84	745.19	1424.27
1971 – 2000 (30 years)	AIC	6.919	7.070	6.757	7.2750
	BIC	1188.033	1494.78	998.31	1853.948
1971 – 2010 (40 years)	AIC	8.164	8.187	8.095	8.251
	BIC	6281.772	6762.13	5855.309	7216.72

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Table 4: Performance comparison of GLM Poisson family with four different links

Forecasting Period	Performance Criteria	GLM family (Poisson) Link (identity)	GLM family (Poisson) Link(log)	GLM family (Poisson) Link (power 2)	GLM family (Poisson) Link (reciprocal)
1971 – 1980 (10 years)	AIC	6.853	6.928	6.803	6.855
	BIC	-9.635	-8.891	-10.139	-9.927
1971 – 1990 (20 years)	AIC	7.202	7.4740	7.049	7.650
	BIC	-29.722	-24.288	-32.77	-21.758
1971 – 2000 (30 years)	AIC	7.066	7.227	6.932	7.475
	BIC	-64.779	-61.34	-68.79	-53.914
1971 – 2010 (40 years)	AIC	8.389	8.637	8.15	8.9311
	BIC	-51.012	-42.80	-60.587	-31.053

Table 5: Performance comparison of GLM Gamma Family with four different links

Forecasting Period	Performance Criteria	GLM family (Gamma) link (identity)	GLM family (Gamma) Link (log)	GLM family (Gamma) Link (power 2)	GLM family (Gamma) Link (reciprocal)
1971 – 1980 (10 years)	AIC	10.653	10.654	10.651	10.457
	BIC	-11.471	-11.456	-11.484	-13.73
1971 – 1990 (20 years)	AIC	10.71	10.719	10.711	10.626
	BIC	-44.691	-44.574	-44.739	-47.44
1971 – 2000 (30 years)	AIC	10.77	10.717	10.776	10.723
	BIC	-84.69	-87.946	-84.776	-87.784
1971 – 2010 (40 years)	AIC	10.969	10.925	10.964	10.932
	BIC	-128.11	-131.560	-128.29	-131.298

Table 6: Performance comparison of GLM Inverse Gaussian Family with four different links

Forecasting Period	Performance Criteria	GLM Inverse Gaussian family Link(identity)	GLM Inverse Gaussian family Link(log)	GLM Inverse Gaussian family Link (power 2)	GLM Inverse Gaussian family Link (reciprocal)
1971 – 1980	AIC	14.3115	14.311	14.311	14.111

(10 years)	BIC	-11.511	-11.511	-11.512	-13.813
1971 – 1990 (20 years)	AIC	14.640	14.640	14.640	14.541
	BIC	-44.931	-44.929	-44.932	-47.922
1971 – 2000 (30 years)	AIC	14.823	14.823	14.823	14.757
	BIC	-85.024	-85.020	-85.025	-88.418
1971 – 2010 (40 years)	AIC	15.130	15.080	15.130	15.080
	BIC	-129.097	-132.781	-129.100	-132.776

$$glm \ EEC \ POP \ CPI \ TMP \ GDP, \ family(gaussian) \ link(power \ 2) \quad (27)$$

$$glm \ EEC \ POP \ CPI \ TMP \ GDP, \ family(poisson) \ link(power \ 2) \quad (28)$$

$$glm \ EEC \ POP \ CPI \ TMP \ GDP, \ family(gamma) \ link(power \ 2) \quad (29)$$

$$glm \ EEC \ POP \ CPI \ TMP \ GDP, \ family(igaussian) \ link(power \ 2) \quad (30)$$

Table 7: Performance comparison of GLM four different families with Link (Power 2)

Forecasting Period	Performance Criteria	GLM Gaussian family Link (power 2)	GLM Poisson family Link (power 2)	GLM Gamma family Link (power 2)	GLM Inverse Gaussian family Link (power 2)
1971 – 2010 (40 years)	AIC	8.095	8.15	10.964	15.130
	BIC	5855.309	-60.587	-128.29	-129.100

Forecast of Electricity Demand per capita

The forecast of electricity demand per capita is performed using the two models. The period of forecast is from 2011 to 2050. The results in Table 8 shows that the forecast of electricity demand per capita for each model are different.

The forecast results of GLM Gaussian family power 2 link function model shows that the growth of electricity demand per capita at the annual rate of 38.9% from 120.4859 kWh per capita in 2011 to 167.3775 kWh per capita in 2050. This is followed by the forecast results of GLM inverse Gaussian family power 2 link function model, which shows the growth of electricity demand from 139.1359 kWh per capita in 2011 to 196.9013 kWh per capita in 2050 at the annual growth rate of 41.53%.

The model with the lowest value is selected to be the most probable model to forecast electricity demand. As GLM Gaussian Family is a simple model and the predicted annual

growth is lower and more preferred to the GLM inverse Gaussian Family. It is predicted that electricity demand per capita would be increased by 39% by 2050.

Table 8: Comparison of the Forecasting of electricity demand of GLM models

Year	GLM Gaussian Family and Power 2 Link Function (kWh per capita)	GLM Inverse Gaussian Family and Power 2 Link Function (kWh per capita)
2011	120.4859	139.1359
2012	121.9138	140.9132
2013	123.3251	142.6684
2014	124.7205	144.4022
2015	126.1004	146.1154
2016	127.4654	147.8088
2017	128.8159	149.483
2018	130.1524	151.1386
2019	131.4753	152.7764
2020	132.7851	154.3967
2021	134.082	156.0002
2022	135.3665	157.5874
2023	136.639	159.1588
2024	137.8997	160.7148
2025	139.1489	162.2559
2026	140.3871	163.7825
2027	141.6145	165.295
2028	142.8312	166.7937
2029	144.0378	168.2792
2030	145.2343	169.7516
2031	146.421	171.2114
2032	147.5981	172.6588
2033	148.766	174.0942
2034	149.9248	175.5178
2035	151.0746	176.93
2036	152.2158	178.331
2037	153.3485	179.7211
2038	154.4729	181.1006
2039	155.5892	182.4696
2040	156.6975	183.8284
2041	157.798	185.1772

2042	158.8909	186.5163
2043	159.9764	187.8458
2044	161.0545	189.166
2045	162.1255	190.477
2046	163.1894	191.7791
2047	164.2464	193.0724
2048	165.2967	194.3571
2049	166.3404	195.6333
2050	167.3775	196.9013

CONCLUSION

This study estimated electricity demand based on generalized linear model from the population, gross domestic product, consumer price index and temperature of Nigeria during the period of 1971 to 2010. The empirical results show that the electricity demand in Nigeria is substantially depend on these four variables. The finding of the study suggested that Nigeria's economy depends on availability of steady and regular supply of electricity.

This can stimulate and expand economic growth in the country. It is inferred that increase in population, gross domestic product have effect on consumption of electricity in Nigeria. Although, annual temperature keeps fluctuating, it influences the electricity demand. Whether the temperature is low or hot more electricity id demanded. In addition, it is suggested that the supply of electricity to the end users would be improved when there is increase in major public investments to provide adequate generation, transmission and distribution facilities. This will encourage industrial productivity and economies of scales for the manufacturers.

It is also important that renewable resources should be used to generate electric power to reduce carbon emissions. The renewable energy sources are fairly abundant in Nigeria and should be fully explored by energy experts to connect disadvantaged households to renewable energy supplies. Furthermore, consumption of electricity by end users should be reformed. Proper efficiency measures should be taken to allocate and distribute electricity, especially the operations of the National control centres should be automated to achieve this. The government should facilitate access to affordable electricity for every part of the Country and provide low carbon energy sources.

The privatization of power generation and distribution companies should be strengthened and regulated to attract foreign investors and support owners of National Integrated Power projects. Another important policy implication is that the four variables plays important role to estimate the electricity demand in Nigeria. One way to control electricity consumption is to adopt power saving appliances by the end users. Although, it is also hard to mention but without charging appropriate electric tariff it is impossible for electricity service providers to keep running and attract more investors and this will continue to affect the quality and quantity of available electricity to end users. In the future studies, it will be desirable to predict and compare electricity demand among the countries in the ECOWAS countries in order to help in developing energy infrastructure across the region and boost the economic activities and address other socio-economic challenges.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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